

H2Avia - Hydrogen in Aviation

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H2Avia – Technology Assessment Scenario and Design Space

H2Avia – Technologiebewertungsszenario und Entwurfsraum

Main Author: Fabian Peter (BHL)

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2. Executive Summary

The research project H2Avia [1] includes all major aspects connected to hydrogen: production, transport, airport infrastructure, aircraft technology adaption, fleet introduction, and an encompassing life cycle assessment. From a technological perspective, H2Avia focuses on a low-risk and high-likelihood scenario. Therefore, the currently most common concepts are implemented, e.g., cryogenic tank placement in the aircraft. Furthermore, the focus is set on the major contributors to transport performance and emissions, leading to the assessment of regional jets and larger aircraft. This document describes how these aircraft are related to each other and the design space for the hydrogen aircraft.

3. H2Avia technology scenario

In H2Avia, a technology scenario was devised (see Figure 1) to ensure a fair and robust comparison of hydrogen aircraft. This is based on three aircraft sizes and respective evolutions. The reference platforms the consortium agreed upon are the Airbus A220, A320, and A350. Similar aircraft are designed in the project. Their designations are regional, short-medium, and long-range reference aircraft (REG-REF, SMR-REF, LR-REF).

These references are the basis for incorporating evolutionary technologies (e.g., incremental weight savings or engine performance improvements). These evolutionary technologies are integrated to achieve a realistic application case for the envisaged entry into service and produce the baseline aircraft (REG-BAS, SMR-BAS, LR-BAS).

In T2.1, principle elementary LH2 technologies (e.g., liquid storage, etc.) were defined. These technologies are integrated and produce the hydrogen aircraft (REG-H2, SMR-H2, LR-H2). They also represent highly likely/low-risk LH2 configurations (e.g., tube and wing, engine on wing, etc.).

The main focus of the technology modeling, analysis, and result publication in H2Avia is the comparison of the baseline and elementary technology hydrogen aircraft. All methods applied to the X-REF, X-BAS, and X-H2 aircraft are homogenous and comparable.

Figure 1: H2Avia technology assessment scenario.

4. Hydrogen technology design space

The introduction of hydrogen opens a large design space for incorporating hydrogen into aircraft design. H2Avia focuses on an integration concept with low risk and high likelihood.

4.1. Propulsion Options

In principle, three options for converting hydrogen to motive power were assessed: direct burn in a turbofan engine, electrochemical conversion in a fuel cell, and a combination of these with a hybrid electric propulsion architecture. The latter was ruled out for the project due to the high complexity of possible architectures and the increased development effort, thereby likely lasting longer until maturity is reached for their application in a production aircraft. The fuel cell architecture features a very high conversion efficiency. However, values currently stated for the thermal management system specific power make this option unlikely for powering aircraft in the size selected for H2Avia (see section 3). The role of the fuel cells in H2Avia is, therefore, restricted to the powering of the onboard subsystems. Consequently, H2Avia will exclusively employ turbofan engines with direct combustion of H₂.

4.2. Tank configurations

The storage of H₂ is the key challenge in hydrogen aircraft design. While its specific energy surpasses kerosene, its energy density is inferior. In addition, the most feasible concepts employ pressures between ~2 to 5 bar and cryogenic temperatures. This makes the storage in the fuselage the primary integration concept in current and past literature. Still, this leaves several options regarding the positioning of the tanks. Since H2Avia lacks the resources to analyze all possible permutations, a design space was defined, and a down-selection workshop was conducted. A pre-selection was made in this workshop, and the remaining configurations were assessed with different scenarios to test their robustness in important aspects. The best-performing configurations (see Figure 2) were prioritized for the specific aircraft sizes.

Figure 2: Assessment of the down-selected tank configurations.

The configurations were dubbed with the number of tanks in a specific position: Front of the cabin (F), aft of the cabin (B), on top of the cabin (T), and below the cabin (B).

- **Priority A:** For the highest priority, each aircraft's configuration was selected based on its specific scenario. Furthermore, the selected scenarios achieved high points in the H2Avia scenario.

A220: FOA2T0B0, A320: FOA2T0B0, A350: F1A2T0B0

- **Priority B (F1A2T0B0)**): A common configuration for all since this will create a good comparison case between the aircraft sizes. The configuration with the highest average value was selected. The selected configuration might not be ideal for an aircraft of a specific size. However, it should yield a functional design in every case.
- **Priority C (FOA0T3B0 vs FOA0T0B3)**: If resources are sufficient, a direct comparison of the top and bottom-positioned tanks will be analyzed.
- **Priority D (FOA1X2)**: At this stage, the outcome of the priority C analysis (top or bottom) will be combined with an aft tank.

Another aspect that plays an important role in the design of the tanks is the insulation concept. In general, foam insulation concepts have been proposed to yield lighter solutions. However, this is dependent on the boil-off requirement. After a certain cross-over point, vacuum-insulated tanks can have a weight advantage. In addition, vacuum insulation offers better thermal insulation, which is advantageous for leakage detection and containment in case of a single-layer rupture. In H2Avia, the modeling will be started for foam-insulated tanks and extended to vacuum-insulated tanks if resources allow.

Furthermore, H2Avia will discuss the question of structural integration of the tanks and whether they should be employed to carry airframe loads. The fuel system will be modeled to a certain extent. Several architectural options are possible here as well, but only one will likely be analyzed.

5. Initial hydrogen concept aircraft

The discussed aspects have been incorporated into a group of aircraft spanning the resulting design space. These aircraft are dubbed the “**Initial H2 Concept Aircraft**” and are shown in Figure 3. They are not the outcome of the fully integrated aircraft design, which is a major analysis product of H2Avia. They are based on scaling with engineering judgment, with the goal of visualizing the design space in terms of aircraft size, propulsion technology, and tank configurations.

Figure 3: The visualization of the initial H2 Concept Aircraft

6. References

- [1] Peter, F. N., Habersetzer, A., Nickl, M., Lüdemann, M., Ebner, K., Effing, T., Badrya, C., Haupt, M., Jünemann, M., and Möbs, N., “H2Avia – Project Description,” 2023.